

CORRECT READING RULES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: you will have to sweat a lot when mastering the rules of studying in English . The article examines the rules of reading in English, and these rules serve to improve the reading technique of language learners.

Key words : voice , pronunciation, language position, Articulation power, Diphthong and triphon rule Intonation. If you set yourself the goal of learning a foreign language, be prepared to face many difficulties. One of them is to learn the rules of correct pronunciation and reading in particular.

Some European languages don't have this problem. For example, in German and Spanish, words are pronounced exactly as they are written.

However, if you are learning English, you will have to sweat a lot to master the rules of studying in English . However, do not be discouraged: if you remember a number of rules, there will be no other problems.

At the same time, there is a certain layer of vocabulary in English that you need to learn, because the pronunciation of these words does not obey any rules.

A whole part of the science of languages is devoted to the study of sounds - phonetics. It is studied seriously in specialized linguistic universities.

However, practice shows that without entering such a forest, it is possible to master the rules of study and use them correctly in practice.

At the beginning of English lessons, you immediately realize that the differences between it and your mother tongue, including pronunciation, are huge.

foreign language, first of all, faces the problem of reading and pronouncing English words. Even many native speakers have trouble reading correctly , and as such, it becomes a barrier for language learners. But, nevertheless, it is very important to be able to read and pronounce the text correctly in the target language, as well as to know and correctly apply the rules of pronunciation.

English from scratch, it is important to learn the English alphabet first. It consists of 26 letters (6 vowels, 20 consonants) .

Beginners should learn the correct pronunciation of all sounds, because English is different from Russian (but there are similarities). To pronounce correctly , you need to train your mouth and pronounce.

After establishing the pronunciation of sounds, it is necessary to learn the basic rules of reading vowels and consonants. Transcription during reading can be in English or Russian. Use dictionaries for reading comprehension, not online translators.

For example:

Some letter combinations are pronounced as one sound.

In Russian, a soft sign is used to soften the sound, in English there is no such sign. Instead, the transcription shows the position of the letter in the word or symbol.

In fact, English is much easier than Russian, because there are no cases or declensions, and it is not difficult to speak it (if you practice). The difficulty arises due to the fact that the pronunciation of the familiar native language is different from the learned one.

and sounds of the English language are directly related to their transcription (recording the sound of certain letters or words). In turn, transcription depends on the rules of reading.

In English:

- 44 sounds;
- 12 vowel sounds;
- 24 consonants.

English pronunciation of native speakers is also divided into several parts. It depends on the origin of the carrier. For example, American pronunciation is different from English. And this is expressed not only in the accent, but also in the pronunciation of the same words or sounds. Nowadays, American pronunciation is more relevant because most students speak it.

One of the features of the pronunciation of English words is the position of the tongue. Therefore, problems may arise during reading, because the position of the tongue should be the same when pronouncing Russian letters, and it should be different when pronouncing similar English letters. English speakers use their teeth, lips, and tongue for the desired pronunciation.

They also have several characteristic features:

English speakers speak with their mouths wide open. For native speakers, the lips are stressed when speaking. During a conversation, the tongue is pressed against the lower jaw. English people use the tip of their tongue to pronounce words.

Articulation is also important in reading English. With proper articulation, first of all, your mouth and, basically, the entire speech apparatus will be in a tense state, and the conversation will be tiring for some time. All this is due to lack of preparation and lack of habit, because in Russian the vocal apparatus is in a relaxed state.

For native speakers, this articulation does not cause discomfort, because their mouth is in a normal position. But they have trouble pronouncing Russian letters and words. Again, everything is normal.

It is very important to learn English reading rules. There is a significant difference between the spelling and pronunciation of English letters, words and phrases.

There are a few basic rules to keep in mind when reading:

open and closed joints. There is no such rule in Russian. An open syllable is a syllable that ends with a vowel sound. It can appear in several cases: - the word ends with a vowel (lake - lake); - in a word, two vowels stand in a row (cruel - cruel); - there is a consonant between two vowels in the word (education - ed` ukeishn).

consonants and vowels. For this, it is worth familiarizing yourself with the transcription table. Diphthong and triphon rule. This is the rule of combining 2 or 3 letters that have a certain sound.

If you are tired of studying English for years?

How to read consonants?

Many consonants in the English language do not differ much from the pronunciation of consonants in the Russian language, but there is a difference.

There are a few special features to note. It should be remembered that all English consonants are pronounced only hard, and voiced consonants at the end of words are not pronounced as boring.

Also, the pronunciation of individual sounds has the following features:

The pronunciation of V sound is different from V. The sound (V) should be spoken with both lips, and (V) with only the lower lip.

P, T, K sounds - pronounced with a further aspiration.

About half of the sounds should be pronounced with the tongue touching the upper palate.

How to pronounce vowels: 4 different syllables

There are also specific rules for reading vowel sounds. There are 4 main types of reading sounds in English (E, A, Y, U, O, I). The pronunciation of the sound in a word or phrase depends on each species.

An open syllable is a syllable that ends in a vowel, even if it is not pronounced.

Reading the vowels in such a syllable can be called alphabetic, because often the pronunciation is almost no different from the alphabet:

A - (ei) - lake, care, care, safe, late;

O - (uh)

7 simple strategies to improve your pronunciation

If you want to improve your pronunciation in English, then you need to find the right way. The final goal can be achieved in different ways. We have selected 7 strategies to help you.

1. Determine how you want to sound

There are many different sounds in English. Pronunciation can vary greatly from region to region. For example, Great Britain is small, but there are 17 different accents that can get confusing.

Therefore, first of all, determine where you are going and how long you plan to be there. Try to understand how the locals speak. Practice. This will help you blend in with the local flavor and understand what you are being told.

If you don't know someone who speaks with the correct accent, watch a video and learn to hear and understand native speakers.

2. Focus on the words that get you into trouble

Are you confused by the abundance of letters? Do you sometimes forget to pronounce certain words correctly?

When you feel like you're hitting a blank wall and don't know how to pronounce a strange word, stop, relax, and notice the specifics of that word. Features include spelling, number of syllables, and meaning.

To do this, it is enough to take a long, complex word and divide it into several parts. And then take it back.

common mispronunciation of February is Feb-yu-airy. But if you read it carefully, we see that the r is in the middle, and divided into syllables, we get Feb-ru-airy. However, in the American version, the English r is not heard at all. For fun, you can listen to how February is pronounced differently in the UK and USA.

However, using this method will give you an idea of how to pronounce words.

Don't forget that English words are not always pronounced the way they are written. Practice, keep practicing to improve your pronunciation, and keep a dictionary close by when needed. If it is difficult to divide words into syllables, follow this rule.

3. Read the text aloud and take voice notes

To see progress in any business, you need to track improvement. If you practice pronunciation, train yourself to record how you read, speak loudly and clearly. Try this online service. You can record yourself, share a link to the recording or download the file in mp3 or other format.

Once you get used to the sound of your voice (we all hate our own voice), you suddenly find yourself moving. If you record after a month or a year, you will really hear the changes.

4. Listen to the music of words

We listen carefully to words, memorize and understand songs, the same method helps to master the pronunciation of complex words, listen to their rhythm and the sound of individual syllables. Words change with emotion. By listening to how words are pronounced, you learn more than what they mean.

Intonation affects the meaning of the word. The same word can be a noun or a verb. The stress depends on which syllable is placed or where it is placed in the sentence.

Understanding this will help you pronounce words accurately. For example, the words refuse and refuse. If you heard it as REH-fuse, then we're talking about garbage and this noun, but if you heard it as reh-FUSE, it means "no" or "to give up something" means is a verb.

The main thing here is to pay attention to the use of words and listen. Practice until you can use the words confidently in speech.

5. Conversation with native speakers

If you want to speak their native language, find a way to contact them. If you do not have any English-speaking acquaintances, this is not a reason to give up. In addition, on the Internet you can find various forums or specialized sites where foreign language learners can meet and help each other. For example, the Language Exchange resource.

6. Watch the news

Even if you don't like watching the news, try using it as a good pronunciation tool. Listeners speak more slowly and clearly to convey information to the audience. When you watch the news, you hear English words placed in a familiar context. This allows you to hear them in real life. In addition, news stories use photography and video images to reinforce the message, making it easier to understand.

If you are interested in British English, turn on BBC news, if American, CNN.

7. Make dictionaries your friends

If you don't know how to pronounce a word, consult a dictionary. Download the Merriam-Webster dictionary app to your smartphone to quickly find the word you need and hear how it is pronounced. Or use the Macmillan online dictionary (with British and American pronunciations).

Pronunciation is a difficult subject for anyone learning a foreign language. Try different ways to improve your pronunciation. Whatever works best for you, you don't even want to try some. This is normal! Don't say it's not possible. Take action and you will succeed!

If you set yourself the goal of learning a foreign language, be prepared to face many difficulties. One of them is to learn the rules of correct pronunciation and reading in particular.

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